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Hadrianus and His Wife Sabina

Murat ARSLAN & Nihal TÜNER ÖNEN

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New Honorary Inscriptions from Termessos for Emperor Hadrianus and His Wife Sabina

İmparator Hadrianus ve Eşi Sabina İçin Termessos'tan Yeni Onurlandırma Yazıtları

Murat ARSLAN * Nihal TÜNER ÖNEN **

Abstract: In this article, three new inscriptions discovered during the Termessos Surveys in 2018 are introduced. Two of these document the emperor Hadrianus was honoured through erecting a statue by the previously unknown Nanas and Konoas/Hekonoas(?) *phylai* of Termessos. The other inscription includes an honorary statue made by the city and public councils for Hadrianus' wife Sabina. While these inscriptions contribute through adding two new *phylai* to the four *phylai* known to date in the city (Idalogbasis, Merlastes, Maramotes and Orbles); and, they further strengthen the possibility that Emperor Hadrianus also visited Termessos during his second eastern journey. Therefore, in this article, firstly, the *phylai* in the city are examined in the context of these new inscriptions and a general analytical evaluation was carried out together with these new *phylai*. Secondly, the possibility of the emperor and his wife Sabina visiting Termessos are discussed, considering the honorary decisions taken by the surrounding cities along Hadrianus' route of travel and the dedicated buildings, within the framework of the cities preparations for the emperor's visit.

Keywords: Termessos, Honorary, Hadrianus, Sabina, Nanas and Konoas/Hekonoas *Phylai*

Öz: Bu makalede, 2018 yılı Termessos Yüzey Araştırmaları sırasında tespit edilmiş üç yeni yazıt değerlendirilmektedir. Bunlardan ikisi Termessos'a bağlı daha önceden bilinmeyen Nanas ve Konoas/Hekonoas(?) *phyle*'leri tarafından imparator Hadrianus'un heykeli dikilerek onurlandırıldığını belgeler. Diğer yazıt ise kent ve halk meclislerinin Hadrianus'un eşi Sabina için yaptıkları heykel onurlandırmasını içerir. Söz konusu yazıtlar bir yandan kentte bugüne kadar bilinen dört *phyle*'nin (Idalogbasis, Merlastes, Maramotes ve Orbles) arasına iki yeni *phyle*'nin eklenmesine hizmet ederken; diğer yandan imparator Hadrianus'un ikinci Doğu Seyahati sırasında Termessos kentine de uğramış olma ihtimalini güçlendirmektedir. Bu sebeple ele alınan makalede, yeni yazıtların içeriği doğrultusunda ilk olarak kentteki *phyle*'ler incelenmiş ve yeni *phyle*'lerle ilişkin bir analiz yapılmıştır. Sonrasında, Hadrianus'un seyahat güzergahı üzerinde yer alan çevre kentlerin, imparatoru karşılamak için giriştikleri hazırlıklar özelinde imparator ve ailesine ithafen aldıkları onurlandırma kararları ve ithaf yapıları göz önünde tutularak imparator ile karısı Sabina'nın Termessos kentini ziyaret etmiş olma olasılıkları tartışılmıştır.

Anahtar sözcükler: Termessos, Onurlandırma Yazıtları, Hadrianus, Sabina, Nanas ve Konoas/Hekonoas *Phyle*'leri

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The inscriptions discussed in this article were discovered during the epigraphic surveys conducted in Termessos in 2018¹. These inscriptions are associated with the emperor Hadrianus and his wife Sabina. The first two inscriptions include two previously unknown *phylai* from Termessos honouring the emperor Hadrianus. The third inscription includes a statue raised in honour of his wife Sabina. All three inscriptions were found near to each other and close to the cylindrical pedestals (TAM III/1 38, 39, 40) carrying honouring inscriptions of Hadrianus by different *phylai* (Fig. 1). As is known, emperor Hadrianus organized two journeys to the provinces of the empire, the first between 121-125 A.D. and the second in 128-132². From both the honourings introduced in this article and in other inscriptions related to Hadrianus, it is seen that the emperor had the title of Olympios³. As it is known, this title was granted to emperor Hadrianus in 129 A.D.⁴. It is understood that the inscriptions in Termessos were prepared in case the emperor visited their city during the course of his second journey. The southern coast of Anatolia was definitely included within the route of Hadrianus' second journey⁵. However, the route of the second journey, accompanied by Sabina, after Antioch, which is known to have been visited in the spring of 131 A.D., cannot be precisely followed. It is known that the emperor visited some of the leading metropolis cities of Pamphylia and Lycia⁶ like Side, Perge, Attaleia and Phaselis. On the other hand it is not clear whether he went to the Pisidian cities from here⁷. The inscription on the architrave blocks of the G Propylon at Termessos⁸ indicate the Temple N7 (Artemis) was also dedicated to the emperor Hadrianus⁹. The fact that a cult was founded and a temple was built in the city in honour of the emperor and that he was honoured by statues which were erected by both the people of the city and the council, as well as the *phylai*, together with these new inscriptions, strengthens the probability that Termessos was visited by Hadrianus¹⁰.

¹ Baz 2020, 93.

² For these journeys and travel routes, see Dürr 1881, 99-276; Weber 1907; Halfman 1986, 188-210; Dräger 2000; Mortensen 2004, 179-206; Kaya & Taşdöner 2016; Akşar 2019.

³ For other inscriptions, see TAM III/1.10, 38-40; İplikçioğlu *et al.* 1991, 9 no. 1

⁴ For the granting the title of Olympios to Hadrianus, see in details Birley 1997, 215-234; Witulski 2007, 109-139. For the cities which uses the title Olympios for the Emperor, see. Magie 1950, 1478 ff. fn. 28; Bönisch-Meyer 2021, 458-473.

⁵ M. Dräger discusses based upon the inscriptions at Perge and Attaleia, as well as the phrase *per Asiam et insulas ad Ahaeam navigavit* in *Historia Augusta* (SHA, Hadrianus XIII. 1) that after the emperor had inspected Syria during his first journey, he returned by ship along the southern coast of Asia Minor and from there passed through the Aegean Sea to the Province of Asia. For this discussion, see Dräger 2000, 208-216; Cf. Tüner-Önen 2013, 94-95.

⁶ On this subject, see Tüner-Önen 2013, 93-106.

⁷ Structures, statues and honourings dedicated to the emperor in addition to those from Termessos are known from Sagalassos, Pogle and Kremna among the regional cities. On this subject see, Kaya & Taşdöner 2016, 502 ff.

⁸ TAM III/1.10 (MS 129-138): Αὐτοκράτορι Καίσαρι, θεοῦ Νέρου | α υἱωνῶ, θ[εοῦ Τραῖα] | νοῦ | [Παρθικοῦ υἱῶ, Τραῖα] | γῶ Ἀδρι | [ανῶ Σεβαστῶ πα] | τρι πατρίδος, | Ὀλυμπίω [ὁ νεωκόρος] | τῆς Ἀρ | [τέμιδος Τερμησέων δ] | ἦμος.

⁹ Çelgin 1997, 170-172, 180; İplikçioğlu *et al.* 2007, 45 ff. fn. 1. About Hadrianus-(Artemis) Temple (N7) and Propylon (G) in Termessos, see also Gülbay 2009, 149-151; 182-183. The propylon here is regarded as unusual, forming the entrance gate to the temple, which is located behind it and was later associated with the emperor Hadrianus.

¹⁰ For this subject cf. Çelgin 1997, 124. Also, for another dedication inscription found near the N5 Temple, see İplikçioğlu *et al.* 1991, 9 no. 1: [Αὐτοκράτορι Κ]αίσαρι | [Τραιανῶ Ἀδρι]ανῶ Σε | [βαστῶ Ὀλυμ]ίω καὶ θε | [οῦ] --- δῆμος | [-----] ΤΟΠΕΡΙΝΑ | [-----].ΧΩΡΗ | [-----]ΟΥΑΥ | ---.

Fig. 1. Aerial Photograph of the Location of the Inscriptions

1. Nanas *Phyle* Honours Hadrianus by Erecting His Statue

A cylindrical statue base made of local limestone. It was discovered between the ruins of the Osbaras Stoa (L2), approximately 5 m west of the main pathway that provides access to the theater (O1) and gymnasium (J). A large piece has been broken off from the left edge of the upper part of the pedestal and, as a continuation, from the back. Also, a large piece is missing from the right side of the lower edge. On the upper part (top) of the pedestal, there are two mortise holes for the statue, one small and close to the left side according to the inscription, and the other large and towards the back. The lower and upper edges of the cylindrical base have a protruding profile. On the upper and lower sides of the body, there is a roughly processed and empty area at a certain height. An inscription in Greek of 5 lines was carved on the smoothed surface of the area, which is in the middle of these areas, separated by a light molding and which covers most of the body. The back of the body, which does not have an inscription, was left unprocessed. With its defined form, this is included in the category of pedestals of type A among the category of cylindrical pedestals of which Heberdey gave the drawing (TAM III/1 tab II).

Inv. No: TER2018/32.

Coordinates: 36°58'58" N; Long: 30°27'50" E; Altitude: 1,020 m; Fallibility: approx. 10 m

Dimensions: H.: 118 cm; D.: Upper: 90 cm, Lower: (visible) 100 cm; L.H.: 1.3-3.5 cm.

Αὐτοκράτορα
2 Καίσαρα Τραιανὸν
Ἄδριανὸν Σεβασ-
4 τὸν Ὀλύμπιον
Νανα φυλή.

*Nanas Phyle honoured
Emperor Caesar
Traianus Hadrianus
Augustus Olympios
(by erecting his statue).*

L. 5: *Νανας*(Nom.); *Νανα*(Gen.)¹¹.

2. *Konoas/Hekonoas(?)Phyle* Honours Hadrianus by Erecting His Statue

A cylindrical statue base fragment made of local limestone. Like inscription number 1, it was found among the ruins of the Stoa of Osbaras, about 10 m west of the main path that climbs to the gymnasium and theatre. The lower part of the pedestal is visible, of the upper part more than half is broken and lost. There are various cracks in the inscribed part of the body. Also, a piece of the left side is broken off. The lower part of the pedestal has a protruding profile, and the pieces are broken off from here include almost half of it. There is no mortise hole at the lower part (bottom). Since the part of the pedestal containing the inscription is exposed, the inscription is quite worn and the letters are difficult to read.

Inv. No: TER2018/33.

Coordinates: Lat: 36°58'58" N; Long: 30°27'50" E; Altitude: 1,020 m; Fallibility: approx. 10 m.

Dimensions: H.: 80cm; D.: lower: 83.5 cm;L.H.: 7.5-4.5 cm.

	[Αὐτοκράτορα]	<i>Konoas/Hekonoas(?) Phyle</i>
2	[Καίσαρα]	<i>honoured</i>
	Τραιανὸν	[Emperor Caesar]
4	Ἀδριανὸν Σε-	<i>Traianus Hadrianus</i>
	βαστὸν Ὀλύμ-	<i>Augustus Olympios</i>
6	πιον ἢ Κονοα	(by erecting
	φυλή.	his statue).

Line 6: *Konoas/Hekonoas(?)*(Nom.); *Konoa/Hkonoa* (Gen.). This name is here documented for the first time. Considering that among the *phyle* names previously documented in Termessos, Maramotes (*TAM III/1. 121*) is inscribed with articulus, Merlastes (*TAM III/1.39*) and Orbles (*TAM III/1.40*) without articulus, Idalogbasis both with and without articulus (*TAM III/1. 38*), 57), the *phyle* name here can be taken as ἡ Κονοα φυλή (*Konoas phyle*) or as Ἡκονοα φυλή (*Hekonoas phyle*). The *phylai* mentioned in both inscriptions were accepted as genetivus, since the names of the *phyle* in the honours of the emperor Hadrianus were given in the genetivus casus in the city.

It is known that honorary statues were erected by *phylai* and dedicated inscriptions were inscribed for Emperor Hadrianus in Perge and Claudioupolis (Bolu), in addition to Termessos¹².

¹¹ For Nanas nomenclature and the genetivus form, cf. Zgusta 1964, 348ff., 1013-10.

¹² *I.Perge I. 115*: [Αὐ]τοκράτορι Καίσαρι | Τραιανῶ Ἀδριανῶ | Ὀλυμπίῳ Σεβαστῶ | σωτηρι τῆς οἰκουμένης |

Six inscriptions recording four different *phyle* names (Idalogbasis, Merlastes, Maramotes and Orbles) have been discovered from Termessos to date. Three of these inscriptions are carved on pedestals of similar shape to those here introduced, and have a similar content¹³. The Idalogbasis *phyle*, which honoured in the first inscription (*TAM* III/1. 38), also honoured a woman named Aurelia Artemis¹⁴. While the name of the other *phyle* honouring Emperor Hadrianus is documented as Merlastes¹⁵; the third honorary belongs to the Orbles *phyle*, whose name was also found in a carved inscription in a single line on the lintel of a building formerly located to the east of the heroon (M) in the southeast corner of the agora¹⁶, definitively according to the oral statement of AV Çelgin, who revised the inscription (*TAM* III/1. 40) and made the necessary corrigendum and addendum (unpublished). Another *phyle* known from the city is Maramotes¹⁷. This *phyle* honours the Apollonian priest M. Aur. Meidianus Platonianus Platon¹⁸. While Heberdey (*TAM* III/1.114) thought that the Πελαγι nomenclature given in dativus casus at the beginning of the inscription including the honorary of M. Aurelius Meidianus Platonianus Varus by a shoemakers' association at the beginning of the IIIrd century A.D., also belonged to a *phyle*¹⁹; he argues that Λεοντίς in the last line of the honouring decision for M. Aur. Claudius Valianus Neon should not be considered as a *phyle* name, but as the name of a small alley reaching to the agora, since it is different²⁰ compared to other *phyle* names²¹. H. Brandt(1991, 276) accepts Leontis as *phyle*. It is known in the decision of the Maramotes *Phyle* to honor the priest of Apollo, that this priest was also archiphyletes. The naming of a member of *phyle* as archiphyletes has only been proven here. R. Heberdey thinks that the official post here is at the head of each *phyle* and accepts it as a concept synonymous in this respect with phylarkhes²². In addition, it is thought that the inscriptions (*TAM* III/1. 114; 864) belonging to the Orbles and Pelagi(os?) *phylai* indicate the structures

φυλή | Ἡφαίστου; *I.Perge* I, 116: ---- φυλή Ἑρμοῦ; *I.Klaudiopolis*52: ἀγαθῆι τύχηι | Αὐτοκράτορα Καί|σαρα θεοῦ Τραϊᾶ|νοῦ Παρθικοῦ υἱ|όν, θεοῦ Νέρουα | υἱωνόν, Τραϊανόν | Ἀδριανόν Σεβασ|τόν, ἀρχιερέα μέ|γιστον, δημαρχι|κῆς ἐξουσίας τὸ | Ἔ η', Ἐ ὕπατον τὸ Ἐ γ', Ἐ | πατέρα πατρίδος | φυλῆι Ἀπολλωνίς | ἀνέθηκεν.; *I.Klaudiopolis* 53: ἀγαθῆι τύχηι | Αὐτοκράτορι Καίσαρι | θεοῦ Τραϊανοῦ Παρθικοῦ | υἱῶ, θεοῦ Νέρουα υἱωνῶν, Τρα|ιανῶ Ἀδριανῶν Σεβαστῶν | ἀρχιερεῖ μεγίστω, δημαρχι|κῆς ἐξουσίας τὸ η', Ἐ ὕπα|τον τὸ γ', Ἐ πατρί πατρίδος | φυλῆ Ἐ Σεβαστή,

¹³ *TAM* III/1.38: [Α]ὐτοκράτορα | [Καί]σαρα Τραϊανόν | [Ἀδ]ριανόν Σεβασ|[τόν], [Ὀλύ]μπιον | [Ἰδα]λωγβασιος | [φυλ]ή; *TAM* III/1.39: Αὐτοκράτορα | Καίσαρα Τραϊᾶ|νόν Ἀδριανόν | Σεβαστόν, Ὀλύμ|πιον | Μερλαστοῦ | φυλ[ή]; *TAM* III/1.40: Αὐτοκράτορα | Καίσαρα Τραϊανόν | [Ἀδριανόν Σεβα]|στ[όν], Ὀλύμπιον | [— — — — —] | [φυλή].

¹⁴ *TAM* III/1.57: Αὐρηλιαν Ἀρτεμε[ι]ν Θόαγ[τος] | [Ἐ]ρμαίου, μητέρα βουλ[ῆς], | κτίστριαν καὶ γυμνασιάρχ[ον] | [εἰς] τὸν αἰῶνα, γυναικῆ ἱερέω[ς] | Ἀπόλλωνος διὰ βίου Μάρ(κου) Αὐρη(λίου) | [Μ]ειδιανοῦ Πλατωνιανοῦ Πλάτωνος, | κτίστου καὶ γυμνασιάρχου, | ἡ Ἰδαλωγβασιος | φυλή. Also see Canali de Rossi 2007, 67 no. 37a. L. Zgusta emphasizes that the *phyle* nomenclature here is in genetivus casus and gives its nominativus as Idalogbasis. Zgusta 1964, 191 ff.; 451-457. W. Ruge (1914, 872) accepted Ἰδαλωγβασιος as *nominativus*.

¹⁵ Zgusta 1964, 311; 904-2.

¹⁶ *TAM* III/1.864: φυλῆς | Ορβλητος. Zgusta 1964, 379;1102-2.

¹⁷ Zgusta 1964, 296; 873-1.

¹⁸ *TAM* III/1.121: ἱερέα Ἀπόλλωνος | διὰ βίου Μάρ(κον) Αὐρη(λίου) | Μειδιανόν Πλατωνιανόν | Πλάτωνα, | κτίστην | καὶ γυμνασιάρχον | εἰς τὸν | αἰῶνα, | ἡ Μαραμοτου | φυλή | τὸν ἀρχιφυλέτην | καὶ φιλόπατριν.

¹⁹ *TAM* III/1.114: Πελαγι. | ἱερέα θεᾶς Ῥώ|μης Σεβαστῆς | καὶ Διὸς Σολυμέ|ως διὰ βίου Μάρ(κον) | Αὐρη(λίου) Μειδιανόν | Οὐᾶρον οἱ κατὰ|πόλιν τεχνεῖται | σκυτεῖς τὸν ἴδι|ον αὐτῶν εὐεργέτην.

²⁰ This difference is that all of the *phyle* designations documented in the city, including the new inscriptions, are of a local character.

²¹ *TAM* III/1.101: [ἀρχιερέα] τοῦ Σεβαστοῦ | [εὐσεβῆ, ἔνδ]οξον, Μάρ(κον) Αὐρη(λίου) Κλ(αύδιον) | [Οὐαλιανόν Ν]έωνα, πατέρα | [Μάρ(κου) Αὐρη(λίου) Κ]λ(αυδίου) Οὐαλιανοῦ Νεωνιανοῦ | [.....]οις, ἀρχιερέως τοῦ Σεβα|[στοῦ, τοῦ] πρώτου ἀπὸ αἰῶνος | [ι(ερέως) Τερμησ(?)]σοῦ, ι(ερέως) Ἡλίου διὰ βίου, | [Μάρ(κος) Αὐρη(λίου)] Μελήσανδρος Ἑρμαίου, | [τὸν φίλ]ον καὶ ἐν πᾶσι | [εὐεργ]γέτην. | [— — (?)] Λεοντίς. Heberdey 1934, 741, 761.

²² Heberdey 1934, 761. For authorized officers and management in the *phylai*, see also Kunnert 2012, 260-268.

in which these *phylai* met and their ownership of property²³.

Together with those documented in the new inscriptions, the number of *phyle* in Termessos is increased to six. It is unclear whether the Pelagi(os) and Leontis nomenclatures correspond to a *phyle*. Chr Marek (2002, 48-50) suggests that the *phyle* organizations in the cities of Asia Minor, as “regional units” may have had a similar character to the *demos* system of Classical Athens, based upon the inscription found in Claudiupolis that lists the 12 *phylai* and archons honouring the emperor Septimius Severus through erecting a statue. Since all the inscriptions documented for Termessos belong to the Roman Imperial Period, it is difficult to say anything about when such a foundation was first established in the city²⁴. U. Kunnert (2012, 173) points out that there are very few examples of naming *phylai* according to people who are not members of the city’s ruling families, as in Termessos, and based upon the fact that the naming of the Idalogbasis *phyle*, documented through two inscriptions, had been used for at least a hundred years, he asserts that ruler’s name of the *phyle* in the *phyle* naming cannot be mentioned. According to him, these people should be among the *euergetes* of the city²⁵. This determination can also be accepted in the inscriptions introduced here for the people named Nanas and Konoas/Hekonoas(?), who gave their names to these *phylai*.

3. Sabina Augusta Honoured by a Statue

A cylindrical statue base made of local limestone. Like the other two finds, it was found among the ruins of the Stoa of Osbaras, east of the main pathway climbing to the upper gymnasium and theatre. About half of the pedestal is broken vertically and a large piece is missing from the top. There are large mortise holes in the top and bottom. There is a deep slot in the shape of a horseshoe, which is understood to have been made for a specific purpose, on the back side of the top.

Inv. No: TER2018/31.

Coordinates: Lat:36°58’58” N; Long: 30°27’50” E; Altitude: 1,020 m; Fallibility: app. 10 m.

Dimensions: H.: 221 cm; D.: Upper: 60 cm, Lower: 79 cm; L.H: 4-4,5 cm.

Σαβείν[αν]

Σεβαστ[ήν]

ἡ βου[λή]

4 καὶ ὁ δῆ[μος]

Boule and demos

honoured

Sabina Augusta

(by erecting her statue).

²³ Heberdey 1934, 747. Concerning the meeting areas of the *phylai* see also Kunnert 2012, 269-272.

²⁴ However, considering that all of the nomenclatures are of local character, it can be thought that it is a foundation predating the Imperial Period. On the Hellenistic Period urban institutions in Termessos, see Brandt 1992, 51 ff.

²⁵ On the naming of *phylai*, see also Kunnert 2012, 234-256.

The erection of this pedestal honoring Hadrianus' wife Sabina should also be associated with the emperor's journey. There is no certain evidence that Sabina accompanied her husband on his first journey to the East between 121 and 125 A.D.²⁶. However, it becomes certain from the poems²⁷ carved on the left foot of the statue of Memnon by the poet Balbilla²⁸, who accompanied them in Thebai during his journey to Egypt in 130 A.D. that Sabina was with the emperor on his second journey. Many cities on Hadrianus' travel route had statues erected and honoured both the emperor and the women of the empire, regardless of whether they were visited by Hadrianus himself and his entourage. Apart from Sabina, Traianus' wife Plotina, his sister Ulpia Marciana, his niece and also Hadrianus' mother-in-law Matidia and Hadrianus' sister Domitia Paulina stand out among the mentioned palace women honoured in connection with Hadrianus' journeys. Honoraries for each of the women of the palace were found in Perge, Attaleia and Phaselis, in cities close to Termessos²⁹.

The inscription introduced here is the first inscription mentioning Sabina discovered at Termessos. Sabina is mentioned with the title of 'Augusta' in this inscription. It is accepted that Sabina was upgraded to this title in 128 A.D., when Hadrianus was described as *pater patriae*³⁰. While Sabina is mentioned as Augusta in the inscriptions of Attaleia³¹ and Magydos³², she was described as Nea Hera Augusta at Phaselis³³, Patara³⁴ and Tlos³⁵.

As a result, the people of Termessos seem to have completed all kinds of preparations in case the emperor would visit their city during his second journey, with the structures they dedicated to the emperor Hadrianus and the honoraries they raised for both the emperor and his wife Sabina. At the moment it is impossible to arrive at a certain conclusion as to if the emperor visited Termessos or not. But it is highly probable.

²⁶ Although Aelius Spartianus' account about the unusual relations between Sabina and the *praefectus praetorio* Gaius Septicius Clarus and the famous biographer Suetonius Tranquillus while Hadrian was in Britain caused the inference that Sabina did not accompany the emperor on this journey, but was in Rome, it seems highly unlikely that it continued in this way over five years.

²⁷ Bernard 1960, No. 28-31.

²⁸ Concerning Balbilla, court poet of Hadrianus, see Plant 2004, 151-154.

²⁹ For the inscriptions in Perge that Plancia Magna dedicated to Emperor Traianus' wife Plotina, his sister Ulpia Marciana, and his niece Matidia, and Hadrianus' wife Sabina, in connection with Hadrianus' East Journey, see *I. Perge* I. 131 ff.; For the honorary of Domitia Paulina by Ioulia Sancta in Attaleia, see *IGR* III no. 773 and for the honorary of Sabina (?) see *SEG* VI no. 649; For the dedications in Phaselis in the name of Plotina Augusta, Sabina, Matidia and Domitia Paulina, see *TAM* II 1190; Adak *et al.* 2005, 10 no. 7 and Tüner-Önen 2013, 97-99.

³⁰ Eck 1982, 217-229; Brennan 2018, 89 ff.

³¹ *SEG* VI 649: [Σεβ]αστήν Σ[αβείνην ?].

³² Adak & Atvur 1999, 63: Σ[εβ]αστήν | Σ[αβ]εῖναν | Ἰ[ο]υλία | Σ[ά]νκτα.

³³ Tüner-Önen 2013, 97 no. 1: Σαβείνα νέα | Ἡρα vac. Σεβ[α]σ[τ]ή].

³⁴ *TAM* II 412: Σαβείνη | Σεβαστή | νέα Ἡρα.

³⁵ *TAM* II 560: Σαβείνη | Σεβαστή | νέα Ἡρα | Οὐελία Πρόκ[α] | [καὶ] Κλαύδιος | [Φλα]ουιανός.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Adak M. & Atvur O. 1999, "Epigraphische Mitteilungen aus Antalya II: Die pamphyliche Hafenstadt Magydos". *EA* 31, 53-68.
- Adak M., N. Tüner & S. Şahin 2005, "Neue Inschriften aus Phaselis I". *Gephyra* 2, 1-20.
- Akşar A. 2019, "İmparator Hadrianus ve Anadolu Gezileri: Seyahatlerinin Amacı ve Güzergahl". *Amisos* 4/6, 1-14.
- Baz F. 2020, "2018 Yılı Termessos Epigrafik Yüzeý Araştırmasının Genel Sonuçları". *AST XXXVII/2*, 91-97.
- Birley A. R. 1997, *Hadrian. Restless Emperor*. London – New York.
- Bönisch-Meyer S. 2021, *Dialogangebote. Die Anrede des Kaisers jenseits der offiziellen Titulatur (Impact of Empire 39)*. Leiden-Boston.
- Brandt H. 1992, *Gesellschaft und Wirtschaft Pamphylens und Pisidiens im Altertum*. Bonn.
- Brennan T. C. 2018, *Sabina Augusta: An Imperial Journey. Women in Antiquity*. Oxford-New York.
- Canali de Rossi F. 2007, *Filius publicus: yios tēs poleōs e titoli affini in iscrizioni greche di età imperiale*. Herder.
- Çelgin A. V. 1997, *Termessos Tarihi*. İstanbul.
- Dräger M. 2000, "Überlegungen zu den Reisen Hadrians durch Kleinasien". *Klio* 82/1, 208–216.
- Dürr J. 1881, *Die Reisen des Kaisers Hadrian*. Wien.
- EA Epigraphica Anatolica. Zeitschrift für Epigraphik und historische Geographie Anatoliens*. Bonn.
- Eck W. 1982, "Hadrian als pater patriae und die Verleihung des Augustatitels an Sabina". Ed. G. Wirth, *Romanitas-Christianitas. Festschrift für Straub*. Berlin – New York, 217-229.
- Gülbay O. 2009, *Anadolu'da İmparator Hadrianus Dönemi İmar Faaliyetleri*. Yayımlanmamış Doktora Tezi, Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi. İzmir.
- Halfman H. 1986, *Itinera Principum, Geschichte und Typologie der Kaiserreisen im Römischen Reich*. Stuttgart.
- Heberdey R. 1934, "Termessos". *RE V/A*, 1 732-775.
- I. Klaudiupolis* Becker-Bertau F. 1986, *Die Inschriften von Klaudiupolis (IK 31)*. Bonn.
- IG Inscriptiones Graecae, I-XIV*. Berlin.
- I. Perge I* Şahin S. 1999, *Die Inschriften von Perge I (IK 54)*. Bonn.
- İplikçioğlu B., G. Çelgin & A. V. Çelgin 1991, *Epigraphische Forschungen in Termessos und seinem Territorium I*. Wien.
- İplikçioğlu B., G. Çelgin & A. V. Çelgin 2007, *Epigraphische Forschungen in Termessos und seinem Territorium IV*. Wien.
- Kaya M. A. & Taşdöner K. 2016, "Roma İmparatoru Hadrianus ve Anadolu: Geziler, Eyaletler ve Kentler". Eds. B. Takmer et al. *Vir Doctus Anatolicus: Studies in Memory of Sencer Şahin*. İstanbul, 494-513.
- Kunnert U. 2012, *Bürger unter sich. Phylen in den Städten des kaiserzeitlichen Ostens*. Basel.
- Magie D. 1950, *Roman Rule in Asia Minor*. Princeton.
- Marek Chr. 2002, "Die Phylen von Klaudiupolis, die Geschichte der Stadt und die Topographie Ostbithynien". *Museum Helveticum* 59, 31-50.
- Mortensen S. 2004, *Hadrian. Eine Deutungsgeschichte*. Bonn.
- Plant I. M. 2004, *Women Writers of Ancient Greece and Rome. An Anthology*. Norman.
- RE Paulys Real-Encyclopaedie der classischen Altertumswissenschaft. Stuttgart*.
- Ruge W. 1914, "Idalogbasios". *RE IX/1*, 872.
- SEG Supplementum Epigraphicum Graecum*. Amsterdam.
- TAM Tituli Asia Minoris*. Vindobonae.
- Tüner-Önen N. 2013, "Hadrians Reisen im östlichen Mittelmeer anhand neuer Inschriften aus Phaselis". *Adalya XVI*, 93-106.
- Weber W. 1907, *Untersuchungen zur Geschichte des Kaiser Hadrianus*. Leipzig.
- Witulski T. 2007, *Kaiserkult in Kleinasien. Die Entwicklung der kultisch-religiösen Kaiserverehrung in der römischen Provinz Asia. Von Augustus bis Antoninus Pius*. Göttingen.
- Zgusta L. 1964, *Kleinasiatische Personennamen*. Prag.